

Nitromethane as a Polar Solvent: Part III. A Study of Acid-base Neutralisation Reactions using Potentiometric Methods and Visual Indicators

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Acid-base neutralisation reactions have been studied in nitromethane potentiometrically and also with the help of visual indicators crystal violet, malachite green, methyl orange, methyl red, dimethyl yellow, neutral red and bromothymol blue. Strength of various acids in this solvent has been compared by measuring the intensity of the colour developed with similar quantities of different acids using a colorimeter.

In parts I and II of the series,^{1,2} some work on nitromethane as a solvent has been reported and based upon the conductometric studies of various Lewis acids, protonic acids and bases, its autoionisation has been proposed as:

This has been further confirmed by carrying out acid-base neutralisation reactions, by isolating the neutralisation products³ and on the basis of solvate formation¹ in the solvent. However, if the proposed acidic and the basic species are real, it should be possible to study their neutralisation reactions potentiometrically and with the help of visual indicators.

The acid-base titrations in various non-aqueous solvents with the the aid of indicator dyes constitute a very convenient method for the determination of acids and bases. Acetic acid⁴⁻¹¹, methyl alcohol^{11,15-16}, ethyl alcohol^{9,16-18}, acetone¹⁹⁻²¹, acid chlorides¹⁹⁻²⁶ and

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dimethyl formamide²⁷ are some of the solvents which have been used for this purpose. The colour changes of an acid-base indicator in water usually depend upon pH or the relative concentration of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions in solution. In the solvents other than water, the colour of the indicator solution depends upon the relative concentration of the cations and the anions specific to the solvent. Potentiometric methods which are also employed to detect the end-point in acid-base neutralisation reactions are considered to be more precise and are applicable even in the case of coloured solutions.

Streuli²⁸ has carried out acid-base titrations in nitromethane, using a potentiometric set up to detect the endpoint, with perchloric acid as acidic titrant but he prepared the solution from 72% aqueous perchloric acid. Similarly Chatten and Harris²⁹ have titrated phenothiozenes in nitromethane and prepared perchloric acid solution from 72% aqueous reagent. Fritz and others³⁰ have used a mixture of nitromethane and acetic anhydride as the medium employing acetous perchloric acid as titrant. Hall³¹ has also tried non-aqueous titrations in nitromethane with a number of bases but has employed perchloric acid in dioxane solution.

The present work constitutes a study of acid-base neutralisation reactions in nitromethane where the end point has been detected with the aid of internal indicators and also using a potentiometric set up. The strength of various acids and bases has been compared on the basis of the intensity of colour in the case of internal indicators and the potential jump in the case of potentiometric titrations.

It has already been suggested¹ that the Lewis acids like antimony(V) chloride form solvates with the solvent nitromethane which subsequently ionize as:

Protonic acids also increase the concentration of the cations characteristic of the solvent and thus both Lewis acids and protonic acids are expected to act as acids in this medium. Since nitromethane has been established as a protonic solvent, it is of interest to study acid-base neutralisation reactions with the aid of visual indicators.

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Crystal violet is a member of triphenyl methane dyes and possesses a tertiary amino group. It has been extensively employed as an indicator in water, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, acetyl chloride, benzoyl chloride and ethyl acetate. Its colour in acidic and basic solutions in water is given in Table I, which indicates its usefulness as an indicator. It has a violet colour in basic solutions and on addition of acidic solutions, the colour changes to yellow through blue and green. Anhydrous solutions of fluorosulphuric acid, sulphuric acid, antimony (V) chloride and tin (IV) chloride have been used as acids against the bases α -picoline, quinoline, dimethyl aniline and pyridine. Results of acid-base titrations with fluorosulphuric acid as titrant are given in Table II.

TABLE I

Change in colour of indicators in acidic and basic solutions in water and nitromethane

Indicator	Colour in water	Aqueous solution		Colour in nitromethane	Nitromethane solution	
		pH	colour change		Colour in acidic solution	Colour in basic solution
Crystal violet	Violet	0.0-2.0	Green to blue	Violet	Yellow	Violet
Bromo thymol blue	Yellow	6.0-7.6	Yellow to blue	Yellow	Pink	Yellow
Methyl orange	Yellowish orange	3.1-4.4	Red to yellow	„	Red	Yellow
Dimethyl yellow	Insoluble	2.9-4.0	Red to yellow	Light orange	Red	Yellow
Methyl red	Light yellow	4.2-6.3	—do—	Red	Reddish pink	Light orange
Neutral red	Purple	6.8-8.0	—do—	Pink	Bluish violet	—do—
Malachite green	Green	11.5-14.0	Blue to colourless	Green	Yellow	Green

TABLE II

The result of acid-base neutralisation reactions with fluorosulphuric acid using crystal violet as indicator in nitromethane

Titrant	Base	Titrant concentration (g. eq./litre)	Weight of base	Gm. equivalents titrated $\times 10^4$		% error	Colour of indicator at end point
				Theoretical	Experimental		
Fluorosulphuric acid	Pyridine	.1493	0.0615	7.78	7.80	0.26	Green
-do-	α -Picoline	.2986	0.0651	9.15	9.11	0.44	„
-do-	Dimethylaniline	.1493	0.1065	8.80	8.76	0.45	Yellowish green
-do-	Quinoline	.2986	0.1293	10.00	9.98	0.20	Green

Sodium nitromethane, the counterpart of sodium hydroxide in water, may be the strongest base in nitromethane but due to its insolubility it has not been employed for acid-base titrations and the organic tertiary bases which act as solvo bases in this medium have been used.

Methyl orange, dimethyl yellow and methyl red are also important indicator dyes and have been widely employed in both aqueous and non-aqueous titrations. These exhibit red to pale red colour in acidic solutions and with the exception of methyl red which has a light orange colour, they have a yellow colour in basic solutions. The colour changes at the end-point in nitromethane are similar to those in water. Therefore, on the basis of the analogy with water, the protonic nature of the solvent can be inferred. Fluoro-sulphuric acid, sulphuric acid, antimony (V) chloride and tin (IV) chloride have been

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employed as acids against the bases α -picoline, dimethylaniline, pyridine and quinoline. The indicators mentioned have been successfully used and the results are within the experimental error.

Fig. 1. Spectrophotometric titrations of various sulphonic acid type bases in nitromethane.

FIG. 1

Fig. 2. Spectrophotometric titrations of sulphonic acid type bases in nitromethane.

FIG. 2

Malachite green is another indicator which is useful in non-aqueous titrations. In pure nitromethane it gives a green, in acidic solution a yellow and in basic solution a green colour. The colour change at the end-point is quite sharp. The same acids and bases as used in earlier cases, have been titrated with this indicator also and results are well within the experimental error.

The neutralisation reactions with the solutions of Lewis acids may be represented as:

where L and B are the Lewis acid and base respectively.

In the case of protonic acids, the neutralisation reactions may be represented as:

The colour of an indicator depends upon the concentration of the cations or anions characteristic of the solvent. In the case of nitromethane which has been indicated to be protonic in nature, the intensity of the colour will naturally depend upon the concentration of the hydrogen ions or the so called apparent pH of the solution. Using same amount of indicator solutions and acids, strength of various acids has been compared with the aid of colorimeter. Malachite green, crystal violet, methyl red, neutral red, dimethyl yellow, methyl orange and bromo thymol blue have been employed as indicators. From the optical density and percentage transmission (Table III) the protonic acids have been arranged in the order of decreasing strength as:

TABLE III

Optical density of the solutions of various acids in nitromethane

Indicator	Malachite green	Crystal violet	Methyl red	Neutral red	Dimethyl yellow	Methyl orange	Bromo thymol blue
HSO ₃ F	0.3	0.48	0.46	0.36	0.90	0.22	0.9
H ₂ SO ₄	0.25	0.41	0.41	0.31	0.72	0.18	0.73
HCOOH	0.13	—	0.22	0.15	0.40	—	—
CH ₃ COOH	0.095	—	0.16	0.125	0.3	—	—

Potentiometric titrations: The plots of potentiometric titrations of n-butylamine, pyridine, triethylamine and piperidine against fluorosulphuric, sulphuric and formic acids respectively are presented in figures 1 to 3. Saturated calomel electrode and platinum

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titration of formic acid against bases in nitromethane

FIG. 3

Fig. 4. Potentiometric titration of n-butylamine against bases in nitromethane

FIG. 4

electrode with chloranil have been used as reference and hydrogen ion indicator electrodes. As in the normal course of potentiometric titrations in water, there is a small change in the electromotive force (e.m.f.) on the addition of the base to the acid both in nitromethane

solution. The rate of change of e.m.f. increases as base/acid molar ratio approaches 1 : 1 where the curve is the steepest and on further addition of the base the rate of change of e.m.f. decreases and gradually the curve becomes almost parallel to the base line. Similar results are obtained if $\Delta E/\Delta V$ is plotted against base/acid molar ratio. However, in the

FIG. 5

case of sulphuric acid, another break at base/acid molar ratio of 2:1 is observed indicating that sulphuric acid acts as a dibasic acid. It is interesting to note that the basic strength of all these bases is somewhat levelled which may be due to the protonation of bases as a result of the protonic nature of the solvent. The order of acid strength is the same as described earlier considering the potential drop as a criterion of their strength.

Potentiometric titrations of piperidine, triethylamine and n-butyl amine against antimony(V) chloride are presented in figure 4 and with tin(IV) chloride in figure 5. On the addition of a solution of the base to a solution of the Lewis acid, there is a small change in the e.m.f. but as the base/acid molar ratio approaches 1 : 1 there is a sharp change. The maximum change occurs at molar ratio 1 : 1 beyond which the rate of change of e.m.f. decreases. Although tin(IV) chloride has a tendency to acquire hexa covalency and can act as a dibasic acid yet in the present case it acts as a mono basic acid. It is just possible that nitromethane may act as a bidentate ligand in the formation of tin (IV) chloride complex. The ionization of the solvate may thus release only one proton.

A similar situation has been encountered in conductometric titrations. The neutralisation reactions may be represented as:

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitromethane, acids and bases were purified as reported earlier¹. Potentiometric and visual titrations were carried out according to the procedure described by Paul and Pahil¹. Optical density and percentage transmission were found by employing Hilger Biochem absorptiometer (C 100/64004) manufactured by Associated Instruments Manufacturers (India) which has a simple shutter to the photo cell, a full scale aperture adjustment and a set of spectrum filters, the filter in use being indicated by its peak wave length engraved on the edge of the disc. The galvanometer scale is a dual one, showing percentage transmission as well as optical density. The tube with pure nitromethane is placed in position and the shutter slowly opened. Necessary adjustment is made, so that when the shutter is closed, the light spot is at zero transmission and when open the spot is at 100% transmission. Filter is adjusted. Then the tube containing the solution under examination is placed and the shutter opened. The percentage transmission and optical density are read directly from the scale.

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